

PUBLISH OR PERISH?
A SYSTEMATIC REVIEW ON FILIPINO GRADUATE STUDENTS' CHALLENGES TO PUBLICATION

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ABSTRACT

The Commission on Higher Education (CHED) in the Philippines has issued Memorandum 15, Series of 2019 requiring master's and doctoral students to publish at least one research article in a refereed publication or a nationally/internationally indexed journal before they earn their graduate degree. Years thereafter, the research productivity of graduate students in the country remains low in terms of completed research, presentations, publications, and citations. There also remains a lack of studies examining the challenges faced by graduate students in their path to academic publishing. The researcher, thus, engaged in the substantive task of systematically providing an inventory of relevant studies as guided by the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses (PRISMA) framework. After a two-level screening process, eleven (11) local studies published from 2019 to 2024 were analyzed to identify the research and publication issues of graduate students and provide recommendations. To this end, four major challenges were identified: institutional and policy challenges, research readiness, publication process challenges, and time and resource limitations. Based on the survey of literature, the researcher puts forward the following recommendations: implementing mentorship programs, organizing research capability-building initiatives, fostering research communities, offering financial assistance and incentives, and improving access to publication resources and information. This review emphasizes the pressing need for graduate school institutions to create supportive environments and targeted interventions

to equip graduate students for successful publication. Addressing these challenges is vital to fostering a more inclusive and productive academic research culture in the Philippines.

Keywords: *CHED Memo 15, s. 2019; graduate students challenges; research publication; graduate studies*

INTRODUCTION

The need to get published has long pressured faculty members and researchers in the academe to produce research innovations and outputs in refereed academic publications. Such relentless emphasis on publication, often touted as “publish-or-perish culture,” is the primary criterion to get tenure, promotion, or gain institutional funding (Moosa, 2018). The process of publication, however, is not a walk in the park and researchers often tread formidable obstacles before they find their byline in a reputable academic journal.

This pressure to publish or the proverbial “publish-or-perish” culture may now have extended beyond faculty members and seasoned researchers to include graduate students. Under the Commission on Higher Education (CHED) Memorandum No. 15, Series of 2019 titled “Policies, Standards, and Guidelines for Graduate Programs,” graduate students across both master’s and doctoral programs are required to publish at least one research article or evidence of acceptance of a research study in a refereed journal (for Master of Science or Master of Arts Academic Track) or nationally or internationally indexed journal (for Doctor of Philosophy Academic Track and Doctor of Philosophy by Research) before they are awarded their degree. This means that, other than having their theses or dissertations, graduate students in the Philippines must also engage in research publication during their graduate studies.

The rationale behind this memo stems from the need for graduate education in the Philippines to meet the demands of the Fourth Industrial Revolution. As Grana (2021) noted, this addresses the need for advanced competencies, innovation, and problem-solving skills to enhance the professional work of graduate students and strengthen national development as discussed in the aforementioned CHED memorandum. With research production as a core component, it positions graduate programs as platforms for mastering specialized fields and fostering scholarly thought (Grana, 2021).

This push from CHED is also a logical extension to the need for graduate-level contributions to research output as the country lags in global research productivity and publication metrics. As cited by Guido & Orleans (2020), the Philippines ranks 5th among 7 neighboring Southeast Asian countries based on Scopus-indexed publications. More concerning is the fact that despite the implementation of this CHED memorandum, the recent work of Roman (2022) shows that research productivity of graduate students in the Philippines remains low in terms of completed research, presentations, publications, and citations.

This gap between policy ambition and research output raises concerns about the preparedness of students to meet the rigorous standards of research publications in the face of the broader structural challenges they face. Unlike faculty members, novice scholars like graduate students often lack the institutional resources, research networks, and publication experience that seasoned academics rely on. They must also overcome limited access to funding and the pressure to master complex methodologies, all the while meeting the high expectations of refereed academic journals. For master's students, in particular, there are inherent challenges owing to their dual roles as students and professionals, often juggling academic requirements alongside full-time employment. Hence for many, the path to publication becomes a trial of resilience, demanding not only academic competence but also emotional fortitude and strategic planning.

As a professor in graduate school myself, these challenges of graduate students are observable and empirically verifiable. However, discussions on the matter warrant further development especially as graduate-level research publications remain low despite the five-year implementation of the CHED memorandum (Roman, 2022). The already few existing studies often remains fragmented, empirical in focus, and lacks a comprehensive synthesis that could bind existing discussions on the matter. While there are scholarly investigations on the challenges of publication from various angles—ranging from mentorship deficiencies to institutional barriers—these are usually addressed in isolation, hence providing rather sporadic insights than a cohesive understanding of the graduate publication experience.

This limiting context warrants the need for a systematic review to consolidate existing knowledge, identify recurring themes, and generate literature-supported, actionable policy insights. To this end, we can move beyond anecdotal observations and fragmented studies to sharpening conceptual reflections and enriching practical reforms to overcome challenges faced by graduate students in their research publication journey.

Research Questions

In keeping with the need to consolidate existing knowledge on graduate students' path to publication in the Philippines, the researcher seeks to pursue this line of inquiry:

- (1) What are the key challenges faced by Filipino graduate students in meeting publication requirements in fulfillment of CHED memorandum #15, s. 2019?
- (2) What future directions can be proposed to address the identified challenges and enhance the support systems for Filipino graduate students in their journey to academic publication?

METHODOLOGY

The researcher has undertaken this research guided by the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analysis (PRISMA) 2020 Expanded Checklist

(Page et al., 2021) to ensure adherence to standard practice of reporting systematic reviews.

Eligibility Criteria. In selecting the studies included in this paper, the researcher used the following inclusion criteria: (1) studies conducted in any graduate school in the Philippines; (2) studies conducted in the past five years, from the time CHED memo was issued (2019) up to the present; (3) studies should touch on the research and publication challenges of Filipino graduate students; and (4) published in peer-reviewed and refereed academic publication found in any of the research databases included in this study.

Conversely, studies were excluded if they: (1) were not conducted in the Philippines; (2) studies did not fall within 2019-2024; (3) studies that do not touch on the research and publication challenges of Filipino graduate students; and (4) the research study is unpublished.

By “studies,” the researcher meant any published study available online including, but not limited to academic journal articles, conference abstracts, and book chapters. The researcher considered all research designs that contributed in addressing the research questions raised in the study—whether quantitative, qualitative or mixed—to ensure a comprehensive understanding of the Filipino graduate students’ challenges in publication. Moreover, the researcher purposively identified 2019 as a starting point for the reference criterion as it is the issuance of the CHED memo.

Information Sources. The researcher searched through digital repositories such as Scopus (www.elsevier.com), Education Resources Information Center (www.eric.ed.gov) and Philippine e-journals (www.ejournals.ph) as well as from academic search engines such as Google Scholar (www.scholar.google.com). These databases were shortlisted as they subscribe to a wide range of journals that contain writings on education.

Search Strategy. The researcher initially conducted a general Google search to gloss over references that could potentially help inform the study as well as to get the maximum possible number of literatures. As Higgins et al. (2019) put it, a broad search strategy is designed to maximize the level of sensitivity to identify potential studies. After looking through the general picture, the researcher narrowed down searches using the Boolean operators (OR & AND) to combine various components of the keywords to look for resources in the electronic databases mentioned above. The keywords include: “publication challenges graduate students Philippines,” “publication requirement grad school” among others.

Selection Process. A total of 10 studies were included in this review. The study selection process consisted of two stages: title/abstract screening and full-text screening. The researcher first looked into the title and read through the abstract to screen whether the variables involved in the resources were of any significance to the research at hand. The eligibility criteria used in the earlier section was used as a standard in finalizing the studies that were included in this systematic review.

Table 1. *Study Selection*

Database/Search Engine	Records Identified	Records Screened	Studies included in the review
Google Scholar	150	36	7
ERIC	78	12	2
Scopus (Elsevier)	0	0	0
Philippine e-journals	132	27	1
Total	360	75	10

Data Collection Process. After systematically selecting the studies reviewed, they were grouped based on the themes that emerged in the search particularly: institutional and policy challenges, knowledge and skills gap, emotional and psychological barriers, time constraints and resource limitations, mentorship and peer support, and financial challenges. The researcher developed a data extraction form to systematically extract relevant information from the studies selected based on themes, reference components, and research design.

Synthesis Methods. The findings from the included studies were synthesized considering the identified themes and research objectives. The researcher opted to write the results both in narrative format and tabular structure to display the results of individual studies and syntheses.

RESULTS DISCUSSION

After rigorous search and review of existing literature that fit within the parameters of this study, four thematic areas emerged as among the challenges faced by graduate students in publishing their studies. These are: institutional and policy challenges, research readiness, publication process challenges, and time and resource limitations.

There are a total of eleven (11) studies that qualified in this review as shown in the table below. These are studies that were conducted in the Philippines for the time period of 2019-2024 (from the issuance of the CHED memorandum about the research publication requirement) which touch upon the challenges faced by graduate students in writing and publishing their research. Most of these studies do not only discuss one thematic area but also cuts across other categories. The research designs are varied, mostly quantitative studies (n=4) but there are also mixed method approaches (n=3) and qualitative designs (n=3). This survey of literature also affirms the gap earlier established in this paper concerning the limited studies conducted and the absence of published systematic review design on the matter.

Table 2. Survey of Literature

Category	Reference(s)	Research Design
Institutional and Policy Challenges	Agatep & Villalobos (2022)	Quantitative (Descriptive)
	Pangket et al. (2023)	Mixed Method
Research Readiness	Roman (2022)	Quantitative (Descriptive-correlational)
	Rosario et al. (2023)	Quantitative (Descriptive-correlational)
	Bautista & Cagalao (2024)	Mixed Method
	Cassanova (2021)	Mixed Method
Publication Process Challenges	Arrieta et al. (2024)	Qualitative (phenomenological)
	Grana (2021)	Qualitative (Content Analysis)
	Quinto (2022)	Qualitative (Policy Discussion)
Time and Resource Limitations	Diocos (2020)	Quantitative (Descriptive)

RQ1: CHALLENGES

Institutional and Policy Challenges. The early years of any academic reform are often the most revealing, as they bring out both the successes and growing pains of adaptation. This is noticeable in the institutional and policy challenges that emerged in the literature concerning CHED Memorandum No. 15, Series of 2019's five-year implementation. Graduate students have reported that graduate school institutions also came unprepared to fully support this transition. With less than five years since its implementation, Agatep & Villalobos (2022) found that essential resources like facilities, training, time, and funding to support graduate students' publication are "moderately available." The works of Diocos (2020) and Pangket et al. (2023) empirically support this as they also raised the lack of information, communication, and technology (ICT) facilities and the lack of mechanisms to develop graduate students' research skills. These findings are consequential as the availability of research seminars/trainings, facilities, access to academic databases, and research grants have been found to be statistically significant in the capability of the respondents to complete their research output (Agatep & Villalobos, 2022).

Research Readiness. Aside from institutional transition challenges, the gridlocks facing graduate students in publishing their work largely stem from their lack of research foundations and readiness to fulfill this requirement. This appears to be a consensus

among the surveyed literature as Pangket et al. (2023), Roman (2022), as well as the study of Agatep & Villalobos (2022) showed “moderate preparedness,” “average research skills,” and “moderate capability,” respectively, in writing and publishing research papers.

While they have taken research courses in their master’s programme, graduate students still report deficiencies in their research skills, particularly in terms of identifying research topic, reviewing literature, research methodology, statistical analysis, and revising their manuscripts (Pangket et al., 2023). The study also captured the students’ difficulty in converting their thesis into condensed versions of publishable research articles. In the work of Roman (2022), it was found that graduate students perform least on areas of statistical analysis, confidence, and instrument preparation. Meanwhile in the empirical study of Cassanova (2021), the problem areas found pertains to inability to select researchable topics as well as limited literature review.

The graduate students’ sense of research readiness is also conceptualized in the literature in terms of emotional and psychological preparedness. Arrieta et al. (2024) analyzed that their lack of confidence and feelings of inadequacy stem from limited research experience. Bautista & Cagalao (2024) framed this by articulating that lackadaisical attitude or the lack of spirit and liveness is to be blamed in graduate students’ reluctance to write their research manuscripts and get published. Pangket et al. (2023) shared the same observation where most graduate students view writing as a sheer academic requirement that could earn them a degree and get promoted rather than an opportunity for intellectual growth. All these negative feelings and attitudes hinder graduate students from attempting to have their works published in refereed publications.

Publication Process Challenges. On top of completing their research manuscripts, graduate students also deal with other technicalities in research publication. One of these hurdles, as Arrieta et al. (2024) pointed out, is identifying research journals where they could publish their work. Arrieta et al. (2024) said graduate students have difficulty in delineating reputable and predatory journals. Some students have also raised difficulty in understanding submission processes of these journals. Looking for reputable publications with no publication fees is also a struggle that graduate students often deal with (Grana, 2021).

Another publication challenge is the intensive process of revisions in academic publications (Arrieta et al., 2024). As Quinto (2022) puts it, conducting research is one thing, but publishing it is a whole new level. Even as their paper is initially accepted, rigorous revision requests from reviewers—which can include requests for additional data, methodological adjustments, or theoretical expansions—can feel overwhelming to graduate students who are new to academic publishing. In Arrieta et al.’s (2024) paper, students reported challenges in responding to these reviewer comments and making the necessary adjustments to their manuscripts. After all, research is an iterative process and

revision especially for publication often requires multiple rounds of changes, each demanding time, focus, and a meticulous approach to detail.

Time and Resource Limitations. Publishing research is rewarding but, as all scholars know, it is also demanding in terms of time and finances. According to Diocos (2020), poor time management has been found to be the most critical challenge that graduate students face in completing their research outputs. As characterized by Pangket et al. (2023), most graduate students especially in the master's level are also working full-time in government agencies like public school teachers. Citing as example the case of teachers, Pangket et al. (2023) said they balance research writing and publication with their work obligations such as heavy teaching load (which sometimes require them to render service even during graduate school class days) and personal responsibilities. Similarly, the lack of financial resources is another challenge especially as grants for publication fees in most universities are limited (Agatep & Villalobos, 2022). This financial constrain could prevent students from submitting to quality journals, potentially limiting the visibility and impact of their research.

RQ2: FUTURE DIRECTIONS

The survey of literature offers various ways to respond to the abovementioned challenges. These recommendations include mentorship programs, research capability building, research community, financial support and incentives, and access to information.

Mentorship Programs. The literature is consistent in saying that mentorship programs must be institutionalized. Faculty members and senior researchers must actively engage in guiding graduate students through the publication process (Quinto, 2022). While graduate studies programs already include research-related courses and advisory mechanisms for thesis completion, there are nuances to mentoring with respect to research publication such as guidance in choosing journal, aligning manuscript with journal instructions (e.g., number of words, template, style), among other processes that entail supervision and close guidance. This type of mentoring should have one-on-one consultations where faculty members provide constructive feedback, collaborative research opportunities, and proactive encouragement, as mentoring has been shown to provide not only technical guidance but also emotional support essential for navigating the demanding publication journey. This addresses both the technical challenges associated to publication as well as ease the emotional toll that graduate students go through. As Grana (2021) and Arrieta et al. (2024) highlighted, faculty support significantly shapes students' experiences and ensures they meet the rigorous demands of graduate-level research.

Research Capability Building. Universities must also prioritize research capability building by offering regular workshops, seminars, and access to research

laboratories that focus on enhancing skills in research methodology, writing, and presentation. Agatep and Villalobos (2020) recommended conducting seminars focused on problem conceptualization, theoretical framework writing, and APA formatting, alongside fostering students' proficiency in crafting results and discussions. Exposure to research conferences, whether local or international, can also boost students' confidence and provide a platform for scholarly engagement.

Research Community. More than skills training, a culture of research facilitated through a research community is essential. While graduate students value mentorship from their professors, peer support is equally important as they do not only need technical guidance but also solidarity from those who experience the same. Interaction among graduate students through structured forums or informal pocket sessions can create a network of peer support, reinforcing mental resilience, and mitigating the sense of isolation often associated with research work. Establishing a research community among graduate students can provide a platform for sharing experiences, addressing challenges, and celebrating milestones (Arrieta et al., 2024). Graduate schools may come up with online forums among graduate students to promote shared learning and encouragement.

Financial support and incentives. High publication fees for reputable journals often deter graduate students from submitting their work. According to Schuman et al. (2023, as cited in Arrieta et al., 2024), providing financial assistance or incentives could alleviate such barriers and even improve research outcomes. It is therefore recommended that universities should offer subsidies, grants, or publication fee waivers, among other financial fee backing. On top of this, it is also recommended that incentives be given to graduate students whose research manuscripts have been published in reputable journals to recognize their hard work as this could encourage them to pursue academic publishing.

Access to information. It is also important that graduate students are given access to relevant and updated information about journals, conferences, and research opportunities (Quinto, 2022). Digital platforms may be maximized to disseminate these resources effectively such as providing updates and announcements on training, seminars, and research conferences in the university website and social media. More importantly, and in response to the challenge of graduate students in selecting journals for publication, it is also recommended that a curated list of credible journals be shared to these platforms so they could avoid falling prey to predatory journals. According to Arrieta et al. (2024), this also enhances students' readiness and aligns their research outputs with publication standards.

Ultimately, by implementing these recommendations, graduate schools can create an environment that supports and empowers students to overcome the challenges of research and publication so as not to “perish to publish.” These interventions not only

fulfill the requirements outlined in CHED CMO 15 but also foster the production of high-quality research that contributes to sustainable development and innovation.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The author(s) declared no potential conflicts of interest with respect to the research, authorship, and/or publication of this article.

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